

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

2nd Policy Report

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MATILDE has received
funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation
programme under grant
agreement No 670531

Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 6.11 – Second Policy Report

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Cover photograph: Christopher Thomson

Approved by Work Package Manager of WP6: Marika Gruber, CUAS on July, 29th 2022

Approved by Project Coordinator: Jussi Laine, UEF on July, 29th 2022

Version: 29.07.2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6912635

Gruber, M./ Pöcher, J./ Zupan, K. (2022): Second Policy Report. MATILDE Deliverable 6.11.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6912635

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Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance Integration and Local Development in European Rural and Mountain Areas – MATILDE

1. Introduction

Rural and mountainous regions across Europe face challenges like demographic change due to a decline of population (e.g. outmigration of young people, low birth-rates) and ageing processes. This in turn has a negative impact on the economic, social and territorial situation in rural regions and consequently hampers their development. For example, a labour shortage imbed the risk of supply insecurities and shortages in branches with importance for rural regions, like agriculture, fishing, tourism and care. MATILDE assumes that international immigration can be an opportunity to counteract these negative trends in rural areas and can be a chance for progress. Hence, MATILDE focuses on rural development and on the social and economic integration and inclusion processes of international migrants, in particular third-country nationals (TCNs).

However, these two perspectives influence each other and are inter-related. This also applies for social, economic, integration-specific and regional development policies, which are additionally interdependent at different governmental levels (local, regional, national and EU) and have various impacts on different groups of migrants such as asylum seekers or labour migrants. This horizontal (integration areas), vertical (government levels) and diagonal (migrant groups) interconnectedness needs to be considered, when it comes to the identification of main policy problems and the elaboration of related policy recommendations and solutions.

This was done in the elaboration processes of policy recommendations and solutions, using a qualitative content analysis according to Mayring (2000) to identify the most important policy problems in the MATILDE regions. The four most important challenges

were found in the integration areas of **“rural development”**, **“economy and employment”**, **“rights and citizenship”** as well as **“education”**, which were described in the policy briefs. Still, further more challenges exist in the other integration areas (housing, health, social connection/cohesion, language & culture, safety & stability, mobility). Some of them inter-relate with each other and/or with the aforementioned four integration areas. Consequently, they are of high relevance for the economic and social inclusion of TCNs as well as the territorial development of the rural and mountainous regions in Europe. Identified challenges are presented and linked with evidence based and validated policy recommendations in the following chapters.

2. Evidence and Analysis

The second policy report will give insights in the challenges of the integration areas **“housing”**, **“health”**, **“social connection & cohesion”**, **“language & culture”**, **“safety & stability”** as well as **“mobility”**. The identified policy problems are based on a continuing analysis process in the MATILDE project. There, a mixed-methods approach was conducted with the help of qualitative interviews, focus groups, quantitative analysis of statistics as well as participatory action research in 13 case study regions with different focus and with the involvement of important stakeholders (see Stakeholder Involvement Plan; Gruber et. al. 2020). Especially for the elaboration of policy recommendations, local, regional and national stakeholders were involved in so-called policy roundtables. There, pre-validated policy problems, recommendations and solutions were presented, discussed, validated and further developed based on the focus of the respective MATILDE case study region. Hence, the policy problems and recommendations of each MATILDE country/region refer to the time of validation, the focused governmental level(s) and type of migration as well as the related integration areas.

Following, the identified main problems in the aforementioned integration areas are going to be explained below.

NEGATIVE CIRCLE OF PREJUDICES, SEGREGATION, GHETTOISATION AND INADEQUATE HOUSING

Ager and Strang (2008, 177) identify *“the fundamental role that social connections is seen to have played in driving the process of integration at local level”*. Therefore, barriers counteracting the social connection need to be addressed. For example, a general persistence of prejudices and negative attitudes of the local population towards TCNs has been identified in Austria, Germany, Italy and Spain, while an anti-migrant rhetoric is assumed as problematic of local politicians (BG, TR) and media (IT, TR).

Ager and Strang (2008) state, that physical safety and the local’s perception on migration is a precondition for social integration. The migration phenomenon is of high complexity and hence often not fully understood by receiving societies which may lead to fears, but also uncertainty, insecurity and instability, as it is figured out for Italy. Additionally, negative attitudes towards TCNs often depend on and are influenced by local stakeholders, as exemplary the case studies of Austria and Germany show. Tensions between different population groups and hierarchization of migrant groups are recognized as a threat for safety and stability, e.g. in Germany and Turkey.

Additionally, possibilities of and access to (low-threshold) encounter (spaces) or information about such encounter possibilities are lacking in the rural regions of Austria, Germany, Norway and Turkey. This is intensified by the segregation of TCNs in specific social quarters (AT, DE, TR), which is inter-related with the challenges in housing. TCNS face poor housing conditions in Italy and Turkey and are concentrated in particular areas (ghettoization) of the regions according to Austria, Germany and Turkey. While rural regions e.g. in Germany, Italy and Spain are generally struggling with a lack of (social) accommodation, the private housing market is evaluated as limited affordable (AT, DE, UK) and inaccessible (ES, UK). Additionally, social housing is restricted in Austria and strategies in cooperation with economic actors are lacking in the United Kingdom.

LACK OF INTERCULTURALITY AND DIVERSITY KNOWLEDGE IN HEALTH SERVICES AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATIONS AND LACK OF OPTIONS FOR LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

On the topic of health, the challenges faced by TCNs are the lack of knowledge or access to health services on the one hand, and the insufficient psychological support on the

other. This also shows the interconnectedness of health with mobility and access to services.² These problems are further compounded by language and intercultural barriers, as interpreters are often absent and TCNs place emergency calls for minor routine medical tasks consequently (Schröder et al. 2018; Kordel et al. 2022).

Language learning in general is an important issue as it affects social inclusion on the one hand and economic inclusion on the other, as TCNs' employment opportunities depend significantly on their language skills (AT, BG, DE, NO, FI). While the United Kingdom requires English language proficiency before the arrival, a lack of language skills is an obstacle for TCNs in daily lives, e.g. in Bulgaria, where official documents and visits to the authorities are delivered in Bulgarian language. In addition to the language barriers, reservations and a lack of intercultural and diversity competencies among employees in public administrations are reported by informants in Austria and Germany.

Therefore, effective language acquisition is necessary both in official integration courses and in daily life. However, there is a lack of available and accessible language courses in Austria and Bulgaria.

Nevertheless, TCNs were often found to have mental and physical health impairments resulting from e.g. war-related experiences, domestic violence and longing for the family (Kordel & Weidinger 2021b). If mental health problems are not adequately addressed, negative interactions with other areas of integration can result, e.g. an inability to work.

MOBILITY AS A BASIS FOR LIVING IN RURAL AND MOUNTAINOUS AREAS

The geographical mobility of TCNs is difficult and often severely restricted due to insufficient public transport especially in terms of connections to rural areas (AT, BG, DE, IT, NO) to access e.g. social and health care facilities, language courses or the workplace. This results in long travel times, which is further exacerbated by high costs and complex ticketing systems, which particularly affects certain groups of people such as elderly, migrants, students or women, as the German case study shows (Kordel & Weidinger 2021a, 2021b, Apfelbaum et al. 2020)

The places are also often widely scattered in the regions, which makes a car almost a necessity to participate in the social and professional life in these regions (AT, DE, ES, NO).

However, since many TCNs do not have a driving licence, they rely on public transport (AT). In addition, obtaining a driving licence is quite expensive in many MATILDE regions and many TCNs have difficulties finding someone to practice driving with or cannot afford an own car at all, thus continuing to face limited everyday mobility (DE, NO).

3. Policy Implications and Recommendations

Building on the results of the of the ongoing analysis processes of the research findings in the MATILDE project and the qualitative content analysis after Mayring (2000) in WP6, the most relevant policy implications and recommendations in the integrations areas of “housing”, “health”, “social connection & cohesion”, “language and culture”, “safety and stability” as well as “mobility” are:

- In order to increase the **access and affordable (social) housing**, municipalities and regions should invest in social housing quantitatively with a higher number of social accommodations, qualitatively with minimum standards and quality control), effectively with housing plans and proper management) and in terms of sustainability by reusing abandoned buildings. **Housing programs, plans and management** should be elaborated by involving employers to reinforce their responsibility, e.g. with company-owned buildings for staff, and by linkages of public investments in housing projects with the availability of social housing. For an increased accessibility to social housing, the **information** should be shared i.a. by welfare organisations, public administrations and NGOs.¹
- **Encounters** need to be facilitated in rural and mountainous municipalities and regions in various ways, e.g. by offering subsidised leisure opportunities or by organising get-together meetings in different neighbourhoods. Those can be the starting point for participants to access a local network. Independently, **up-to-date information** about encounter events, leisure or sport activities, language trainings, cultural events, etc. need to be available, on a platform at local level in different

¹ For further recommendations and practical solutions, please refer to the policy brief “The Impact of Migrants on Rural Development”.

languages (e.g. on the municipal website). There, clubs and associations can also promote themselves. Besides, **mentor or buddy schemes** can act as enabler for social contacts and can personally invite and accompany newcomers as a social bridge to the rural activities and encounters and inform them, how to volunteer in the region. However, joint activities need **encounter zones or spaces**, which should be made available at local level and with low-threshold (e.g. free of charge, without the need to consume and without fees/membership).

- Besides encounter, **information and awareness building** are important to overcome negative attitudes, prejudices and an anti-migrant rhetoric, in order to increase the social connection and stability in rural regions. **A contact person for integration issues** with permanent provision and funding should be established at local or inter-municipal level, networking with relevant stakeholders, volunteers and TCNs in parallel. Also, projects that promote cultural exchange and mutual understanding should be supported. At regional, national and EU level, **programmes addressing racism and intercultural opening** are requested. For example, local and regional media can present refugee testimonials and intercultural initiatives or give information about the migrant's lives. Alternatively, **political strategies** including competence centres, networks, pooled measures can be initialised and offered in municipalities.
- To foster the social and economic integration, language courses for TCNs should be expanded. It is recommended to offer **low-threshold, free language courses and literacy courses in small groups** (AT, DE, BG) as well as **follow-ups** and **on-the-job courses** (DE, FI). For the regions in the United Kingdom, **local informal meeting opportunities** to acquire appropriate language skills and integrate into the local community should be promoted. As attendance at language courses, especially for migrant mothers and single parents, is often linked to the availability of childcare places, regions should also improve **access to childcare** so that adults

are able to attend language courses (AUT, DE, TK), which is interlinked with the integration area “education”².

- Besides the general access to health care services³, more psychologists and therapists need to be trained and motivated to offer their services outside the big cities, and **TCNs’ access to psychological help and in the area of addiction counselling** (cf. Fachkommission Integrationsfähigkeit 2021) needs to be facilitated (AT, DE). needs to be extended. Additionally, **the local administration could use** their space of action to offer asylum seekers an **easier access to health-related services** (§4, 6 AsylbLG, cf. Schammann et al. 2021). This is particularly important in dealing with mental health problems, as therapeutic counselling services are often not available in rural areas. Finally, municipalities are called upon to understand health holistically by including both social and leisure aspects in municipal health concepts, which should be communicated in an interculturally sensitive manner, as pointed out by the German case study (DE).
- **Interpreters** (e.g. of those languages most common among migrant women) should be **available/ready to call in all hospitals and offices**, and hospital staff should be trained in the needs of TCNs as the example of the Turkish case study shows (TR).
- **In addition, public transport need to be expanded** combined with **financial support for groups at risk of poverty and exclusion** and with **alternative and creative solutions** regarding mobility (e.g. ride-sharing). Alternatively, especially refugees may need (financial) support for **(re)acquiring a driving licence**. Offering driving licence courses in different languages⁴ would contribute positively as well.

² For further recommendations and practical solutions, please refer to the policy brief “Education of (young) TCNs as Basis for Economic and Social Integration in Rural Areas”

³ For further recommendations and practical solutions, please refer to the policy brief “The Impact of Migrants on Rural Development”.

⁴ For more details on the recommendations and practical solutions, please refer to the policy brief “The Impact of Migrants on Rural Development”.

4. Project Identity

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FUNDING PROGRAMME

European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme:

H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018-2019-2020/H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Grant agreement No. 870831

DURATION

February 2020 – January 2023 (36 months)

PROJECT WEBSITE

URL: <https://matilde-migration.eu/>

SOCIAL MEDIA

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/MatildeProject>

Twitter: https://twitter.com/MATILDE_Mig

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/matilde-migration/>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/matildemigration/>

Academia: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/matilde-migration/>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Matilde-Migration>

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6. Further Reading

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MATILDE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870831